

Workshop - World Anti-Bullying Forum

Using Art to Engage Youth in (Cyber)Bullying Research: An Interactive, Creative Methodology Workshop

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Sub-Theme: Conceptual and methodological issues in bullying and cyberbullying

This workshop introduces innovative, arts-based methods including but not limited to PhotoVoice, Storytelling, and collaborative Zines to creatively engage youth in exploring and addressing (cyber)bullying. Grounded in the belief that young people are essential knowledge-holders, this workshop acknowledges the challenges of conducting research with youth - particularly in their digital lives. While capturing the diversity of their experiences, we demonstrate how creative methodologies can empower young people to express their lived experiences, unpack complex issues, and envision solutions. Drawing from experiences of conducting (cyber)bullying research among youth in Denmark, Greece, Ireland, and Italy, this workshop equips educators, researchers, and practitioners with adaptable tools for fostering meaningful, youth-centred inquiry.

Participants will actively engage with creative techniques to elicit genuine insights and build trust with youth. This workshop aims to showcase how such methods can be used in distinct cross-disciplinary settings. We will discuss how to adapt art-based qualitative approaches to different cultural and social contexts and involve youth voices effectively in research and policy. The workshop aims to expand participants' capacity to use creative methods as a powerful approach to uncovering and addressing the complex dynamics of (cyber)bullying among youth.

Ultimately, this workshop introduces alternative, complementary approaches that engage the creative imaginations of youth. These methods offer additional pathways for youth to express information and experiences, enriching traditional research methods by enabling them to share insights they may otherwise find challenging to articulate.